

First Stage: Task Assessment

DS3: In the case of defining data access, I think this connection with the software engineer is going to be essential. After the data scientist has the data, it will be possible to work on it, train the model, perform feature engineering, etc.

DS5: I agree, I think the scientist should have this conversation with the software engineer to find out how to access the data.

DS3: I partially disagreed with the statement for data selection. The role of a data scientist consists of analyzing the data and performing feature engineering to train the model. For these activities, I would not involve a software engineer. On the other hand, during data selection, it is possible to deal with incomplete data that you might have to discard or adjust. You may even discover the existence of more data that you still need to acquire. This can lead to a change in how data is being accessed, which may provoke an interaction with a software engineer. However, I believe the data selection process itself falls directly to the data scientist.

DS4: That is exactly why I partially disagreed. Sometimes you have to go back to the data access definition to get data not initially considered.

DS5: I think this is a very exceptional case.

SE2: In the project I am currently working on, we use a collection of documents to train the ML model. These documents were sent to us by customer representatives who are not software engineers, so there was no interaction between these roles. This is why I only partially agreed with the statement for this task.

DS3: This makes total sense. In some cases, data scientists may receive data through spreadsheets. At some point, someone had to export or make them available. It may not have been specifically a software engineer, but someone who knows the subject. I have seen several projects where the data scientist is also the software engineer.

SE2: I do not consider the interaction between software engineers and data scientists very relevant for ML model storage.

DS5: I have a different opinion. It is important that both actors define where and how this storage will occur. This interaction with the software engineers allows the data scientists to understand what infrastructure is currently used for storage, as they are usually not involved in this process.

DS3: I partially agreed in this case. Throughout development, it is possible that team members change, which may harm the improvement of existing models. This can be mitigated by having an infrastructure where artifacts can be properly managed with adequate versioning, which should be created through the actors' collaboration.

Second Stage: Recommendation Assessment

1-) Involve data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements

DS5: It is important to have the business owners during data access definition so that they can explain the data.

DS3: I do not consider this recommendation relevant for collaboration during data selection. I do not think the interaction between data scientists and software engineers is important during this task. The presence of other actors, such as business owners, is more important than this interaction.

DS4: I did not agree with the tasks related to deployment and integration I do not think this recommendation would be that interesting for these tasks. For example, I consider model integration more of an implementation task, just like with deployment, so perhaps the business owners might not be needed. It depends on whether there will be a testing phase for their acceptance of what was developed.

DS3: In my view, any prioritization or decision-making often involves business owners. In some cases, the integration task may involve different teams, and the business owner will be able to facilitate this coordination. I had doubts concerning this recommendation for ML model evaluation, but I decided to partially agree. Everyone must comprehend what exactly will be evaluated. Performance can be evaluated not only in terms of accuracy and other metrics but also in terms of computational performance. There is no point in having a super complex model if it will require a machine with tons of computational power that will not be available. These definitions can sometimes be made together with business owners and software engineers.

2-) Provide ML literacy for all project stakeholders

DS3: I consider literacy relevant, as knowing at least the basics is important for communication. The only exception I can see is during data selection because I think the participation of the software engineer is reduced. I partially agreed on the other tasks because, in the worst case, everyone has to know that a model will be executed, that an output of a certain type will be generated, etc.

SE2: This recommendation is important to improve communication between the software engineer and the data scientist. It is vital to establish a common terminology so that communication flows more easily.

DS3: As I mentioned in the discussion about the tasks, it is a good idea to define the best way to store the model together with the software engineers to make it more easily accessible in the future. For this to be possible, they must understand what model training is and what is actually being stored.

DS4: What you said made me think, but I personally do not see much relevance in ML literacy for improving collaboration during ML artifact storage.

3-) Develop documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points

DS3: I do not think this recommendation is relevant for data selection because I do not see the need for much interaction between software engineers and data scientists during this task. For ML model evaluation, I think this interaction exists, but it is not strong, so I partially agreed with the statement.

DS4: The model will be evaluated based on the documented requirements, so I think this recommendation has a lot of influence on this process. Even if you do not need a lot of interaction between the software engineer and the data scientist in this activity, I believe documentation will be relevant for any interaction that happens.

SE2: Particularly for ML model integration, I find this recommendation very beneficial for collaboration.

DS5: I agree. Especially when defining APIs, this documentation is important for validating what will be done with the software engineers.

4-) Define clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers

DS3: This recommendation is important regardless of how much interaction occurs during each task. Even if there is an activity where there is not supposed to be any collaboration between a software engineer and a data scientist, this must be clear for everyone to avoid someone doing something that is not their responsibility. This recommendation will help define what interactions will happen during the project.

DS5: Even for tasks with reduced interaction, following this recommendation guarantees everyone knows their role and what they must do.

5-) Support interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers

DS4: Knowing about other fields is always beneficial, but I do not consider this essential for any activity.

DS5: During data access definition, having both actors working closely may speed up the process. This recommendation can also help during model integration, as this task requires a lot of collaboration between data scientists and software engineers.

DS4: I think sharing knowledge is always valuable, but I do not consider this recommendation relevant for collaboration during the tasks.

6-) Organize regular meetings for showcasing team activities

DS3: The interaction between software engineers and data scientists will be greatly facilitated if you know exactly what each person is doing and what is happening in the project.

Moderator: Do you see any other advantages brought by this recommendation?

DS3: This recommendation is valid for monitoring the team and exchanging knowledge, as you can even schedule technical meetings if needed. At the very least, these regular meetings to find out how things are going and what is being done already help a lot.